

RADNEXT Transnational Access Summary Report

Project title	<i>Superconducting Fusion Integrated Neutron Diagnostics, SuperFIND</i>
Project TA identifier	<i>TA13-417</i>
General application	<i>Neutron diagnostics for fusion power.</i>
Type of test	<i>Neutron signal response test. Radiation environment operation tests.</i>
Group leader, Institute	<i>Mette Bybjerg Brock-Hansen, SUBRA A/S (primary) and Technical University of Denmark.</i>
Co-authors, Institutes	<i>Torben Hansen, Senior Development Engineer, SUBRA A/S. Ida Skøt Støvring, Development Engineer, SUBRA A/S. Christian R. H. Bahl, Head of R&D, SUBRA A/S.</i>
Date(s) of the experiment	<i>8th – 12th September 2025</i>
Facility	<i>Frascati Neutron Generator, ENEA</i>
Amount of access granted	<i>50 h</i>

Objectives of the experiments

The project aimed to test key performance parameters for a superconducting bolometric neutron detector system. The test detector is aimed at fusion neutron diagnostics for commercial fusion power systems. Therefore, it was important for the tests to be performed with DT Fusion energy neutrons in a controlled environment, where the background and other influences are well characterized. Due to the early prototype stage of the test detector, the selective energy (14 MeV) neutron beam was of higher importance than having access to the full energy-spectrum of neutrons that will be present in a fusion power system at the TF coil position.

The aim of the project was to investigate the following parameters of the test detector system:

1. The dynamic range associated with various flux levels of a 14 MeV neutron beam.
2. The on-going performance and vulnerabilities during irradiation of associated detector electronics needing to be placed close to the detector position.
3. The energy selective sensitivity of test detectors designed with energy selective properties for neutron energies above 1 MeV.
4. The sensitivity to the gamma radiation background present in the bunker during high flux neutron generation.

The prototype detector was in an early stage during testing, and some measurement capabilities were therefore limited during the beam-time. Initial results were achieved for aims 1-3, of the original proposal listed above. Aim 4 will be tested in future work.

Experiment test report

Beam-on measurements were performed from 8. to 11. Sep 2025. Mornings were used to change samples, stabilize the measurement setup and perform calibrations. Neutrons were used primarily after midday and until the evening.

On midday Sep 11, 2025, the filament in the plasma chamber of the Frascati Neutron Generator (FNG) was worn down, and a replacement had to be made. Although the facility was able to replace the filament already early the following morning, it was not possible to resume normal operation until after the end of the allocated beam-time. Two replacement days were offered by the facility to be used later in 2025 as a substitute for lost time. It was not deemed possible by the user-group to be able to make use of these, and the result of this report is therefore based on measurements made over the first three days (35h) of the allocated beam-time.

Setup outline

The tested detector design was based on a cold/thermal neutron sensitive superconducting bolometer described in a previous publication [1]. The prototype detector system consists of a detector sample with electronic contact to a readout system, and a cryocooler-based sample environment connected to a small vacuum-pump. The full setup as placed on the experimental tower near the neutron source can be seen below on Figure 1a and 1b.

Fig. 1. Left (a) shows the cryocooler (right) with the vacuum hose attached. The bell at the top holds the detector sample. The breakout box for electronic contact to the samples as well as the pre-amplifiers for each pixel are placed behind radiation shielding to the right in the picture. Right (b) shows the cryocooler and the target as seen from the top. The flat surface of the cryocooler vacuum bell holding the detector sample is placed app. 2 mm from the outside of the target. Kapton is used on the edges placed closest to each other, in order to avoid electrical contact between target and bell.

Detector samples with both non-neutron sensitive and neutron sensitive designs were tested. Each detector pixel was tested separately, and any matrix-effects of neighbouring pixels were not tested in the current setup.

Neutron measurements

Two types of measurements were performed for each detector. In between most measurements, a test shot was used to find the expected neutron flux at the new source current settings used for each test.

1. Signal test: 1 min with neutrons on, followed by 1 min with neutrons off. This was typically repeated 4-12 times. For some of the series, the source current was varied to obtain higher or lower fluxes of the different shots.
2. Continuous test: Typical measurement lengths of 12 – 20 min, where the neutrons were on. Initially the neutrons were at a lower flux, but the source current was then varied in non-

periodical steps to simulate a plasma burning with different intensities over the length of a full shot in a magnetic confinement fusion test facility.

Day	Samples	Type	Duration	Neutron flux from source (n/cm ² /s)	Notes
1	1 and 2	Calibration shots Signal test	- 3 x 12 min.	2·10 ⁹ - 8·10 ⁹	
2	1 and 2	Signal tests Continuous tests	8 x 9 min 3 x 15 min	5·10 ⁹ - 3.5·10 ¹⁰	Radiation induced instability in electric readout*.
3	3 and 4	Signal tests Continuous tests	10 x 9 min 1 x 19 min	2·10 ⁹ - 3.5·10 ¹⁰	
4	4 and 5	Signal tests	2 x 7 min	5·10 ⁹ - 8·10 ⁹	Source down after two shots.
5	5 and 6	-	-	-	Source down.

* The readout lost connection or stalled during longer measurements at fluxes above 10¹⁰ n/cm²/s. The electronic equipment was moved further away from the source, and reset before every measurement, which solved the problem.

Initial results

Test results are still being analysed, but the following correlations can be formulated on the sensitivity of the test detector samples to 14 MeV neutrons at high fluxes:

For a detector with a non-neutron sensitive design, initial results indicate no measurable sensitivity to 14 MeV neutrons even for high fluxes (1.5·10⁸ n/cm²/s). This is important for development of reference signals for in-situ on-going calibration of the detector.

For detectors with neutron-sensitive designs, initial results show a measurable signal for 14 MeV neutrons with strong indications of flux dependent scalability. Tested flux-range 5·10⁹ – 3.5·10¹⁰ n/cm²/s.

The remaining analysis of the results will lead to a new development phase for the detector, to be tested at the same source at a later stage, as well in a test facility with a broader energy spectrum, simulating the intended for placement in future fusion reactors.

Furthermore, the results serve as the base for upcoming academic-industrial partnerships in the current collaboration, possibly involving more parties to push the technology development for industrial use.

[1] Brock, M.B., et. al, "Superconducting transition edge bolometer for high-flux neutron detection.", *Sci Rep* 13, 22266 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-023-49469-4>

Outcome of the experiments

Please indicate what the experiment is likely to lead to by putting an 'X' next to one or more of the possible outcomes below.

Journal publication	
Data for Thesis	
Follow-up experiment at same facility	X
Follow-up experiment at another facility	X
Other	X

As a RADNEXT user, we encourage you to submit the scientific results of your experiments to journals as well as to the NSREC and RADECS data workshops. Please remember to include the RADNEXT acknowledgment into your publications!

RADNEXT acknowledgment:

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